

The ‘*Study of Man and His Brain*’ Long-term Comprehensive Program in Bulgaria (1984-1995): in Searching of ‘*Harmoniously Developed Personality*’

Georgeta Nazarska

Abstract: *The article examines the 'Study of Man and His Brain' Long-term Comprehensive Program (1984-1995), aimed at activating neuroscience in Bulgaria and introducing a pattern for modern scientific research. The main aim of the study is to analyze whether and to what extent the Program represents an attempt by the late totalitarian regime to continue its previous projects ('Bulgaria 1300' and 'Banner of Peace' International Children's Assembly) and to implement various utopias in the field of medicine, science, education, technology and management, and achieving of its aims. For this purpose, the motivation of various social actors in the establishment of the Program is examined, its structure and functioning are described, the results achieved in the fields of medicine, psychiatry, psychology, pedagogy, informatics, military affairs and cybernetics are analyzed. The effectiveness of the project is commented in comparison with similar activities on both sides of the Iron Curtain. The Program catalyzed reforming of health care and secondary education through transfer of knowledge, technique and technology from the Western Europe and the US, but it could not realize significant social utopias. Its significant impact is the consolidation of Bulgarian neuroscience.*

Keywords: *utopia, social reformism, Neuroscience, totalitarian regime, Bulgaria*

Introduction

Aims and methodology. The article examines the '*Study of Man and His Brain*' - Long-term Comprehensive Program (1984-1995), aimed at activating neuroscience in Bulgaria and introducing a pattern for modern scientific research. The main aim of the study is to analyze whether and to what extent the Program represents an attempt by the late totalitarian regime to continue its previous projects ('*Bulgaria 1300*' and '*Banner of Peace*' International Children's Assembly) and to implement various utopias in the field of medicine, science, education, technology and management, and achieving of its aims. For this purpose, the motivation of various social actors in the establishment of the Program is examined, its structure and functioning are described, the

results achieved in the fields of medicine, psychiatry, psychology, pedagogy, informatics, military affairs and cybernetics are analyzed. The effectiveness of the project is commented both in view of the pursued goals and in comparison with similar activities on both sides of the Iron Curtain.

The mentioned topic has not been researched in Bulgarian and foreign historiography, except for the mention of the Program in media publications. Based on his experience in the field of psychiatry alone, Dr. Rumen Petrov maintains that the Program was aimed at social engineering and served the interests of the communist elite.¹

This article is part of a monographic study on the development of brain research and of Neuroscience in Bulgaria in the second half of the 20th century. Therefore, in the text, the Program is considered as a chronologically late element of this development, which has no decisive significance for the birth and shaping of science and its field. It uses an interdisciplinary approach combining social history, oral history, and the history of science, and uses data drawn from archival and published documentation, periodicals, and the author's personal oral standardized and semi-standardized interviews.

Since the Program was under the control of the military and State Security, and its archive contained classified data, it is currently untraceable, probably ‘collected’ by the cited institutions in the mid-1990s.² For this reason, the history of the Program with its participants, content and guidelines has been reconstructed, on the one hand, through documents searched in public archives (Scientific Archives – BAS, State Archives in Sofia and Varna, Central State Archives and Archives of the Commission on State Security Files) and through the personal archival collections provided, and on the other hand, through the oral accounts of the 10 respondents. The interviewees are quoted anonymously, as the requirements of the ‘Leviathan’ Project and by their personal will, with only their gender and age indicated. The interviews were conducted face-to-face in 2022-2024, only two of them were sent by e-mail. Majority of my respondents were affiliated to the Programm as doctoral students or young sci-

¹ МЕТОДИЕВА, Ю. Социалното инженерство на българския тоталитаризъм е родило шедеври. Интервю с Румен Петров. *Маргиналия*, 17.01.2020. Достъпна на: <https://www.marginalia.bg/aktsent/shedovar-na-totalitarniya-rezhim/>, 11.05.2025; ИВАНОВА, Д. 1984 и Програмата за мозъка: 40 години по-късно. *Свободна Европа*, 01.04.2023. Достъпна на: <https://www.svobodnaevropa.bg/a/32343410.html>, 11.05.2025.

² E-mail from Kr. Pastireva, Departmental Archive of the MA – Sofia, 01.06.2023. In: *Personal archive of the author*.

entists, others participated in its administration, and a few are heirs of its initiators. Wherever possible, memoirs, interviews and biographical publications of already deceased scientists have been used for the purposes of historical reconstruction.³

Context. The full name of the Long-term Comprehensive Program was '*The Study of Man and His Brain with a view to increasing the intellectual capabilities of the person and expanding his creative powers*'. It was launched in October 1984, but its conception dates back to 1979-1980. The initiative came from high-ranking Bulgarian state officials and set several main goals: to study, accelerate and dynamize the pre-genetic and genetic powers and abilities of man; to optimize the social environment and to predict and manage the processes of creativity.⁴

At first glance, the Program represented a reflection of the political, social, cultural and scientific milieu of the decade. Above all, it was an emanation of the efforts of Bulgarian medicine to shape the scientific field of neuroscience, the beginning of which was laid in the early 1960s.⁵ The Program also reflects the attempt of the Bulgarian Communist Party since the early 1960s to use the achievements of the scientific and technological revolution in the country in order to compensate for the economic and technological backwardness of the Eastern bloc and to diversify its ties with the USSR.⁶ The Program also fit into the direction of rapid development of neuroscience around the world and the

³ ЖАБЛЕНСКИЙ, А. Интервью Асена Жабленского П.В.Морозову на 11-й Всероссийской школе молодых психиатров в Суздале. *Дневник психиатра*, 2013, №4, с.1-2. Достъпна на: <https://icern.org/about/the-diary-of-psychiatrist-interview-with-prof-assen-jablensky/>, 11.05.2025; ЖАБЛЕНСКИ, А. Verstehende = erklärende? Темата „политика и психично здраве“ предизвика две твърде различни непосредствени реакции. *Народна култура*, № 47 (1844), 22.11.1991; НИКОЛОВ, Н. Скритите резерви на мозъка. *Студентска трибуна*, № 1271, 16.04.1985; ХРИСТОЗОВ, ХР. Моят живот. София: Етропи 1, 1999.

⁴ ЦДА, ф. 174Б, оп. 2, а.е. 1433, л. 1а-44.

⁵ УЗУНОВ, Г., С. БОЖИНОВ. Кратки бележки върху развитието на катедрите по неврология и психиатрия, 1922-1958. В: *40 г. МФ, 1918-1958. Юб.сб.*, София: МФ, 1958, с. 260-267; ЦВЕТКОВА, М. И КОЛ. Състояние и перспективи на някои проблеми от неврологията и психиатрията, разработени от НИИ. В: НИИП. *Научна сесия, посветена на 20 г. от 9.09.1944, състояла се на 9-10.09.1964*. София: МФ, 1965, с. 6, 9.

⁶ ИВАНОВ, М. *Реформаторство без реформи. Политическа икономия на българския комунизъм, 1963-1989*. София: Сиела, 2008, с. 228-250; ЗНЕПОЛСКИ, ИВ. (СЪСТ.) *НРБ от началото до края*. София: Сиела, 2011, с. 301-302.

so-called bio industrial revolution.⁷ It was a response to the IBRO's efforts to organize scientists in the field of brain research to co-operate on a wider scale, as well as to the WHO to impose a new agenda in global health with particular emphasis on social psychology, occupational hygiene and access to all social groups and strata to health care.⁸ Through the Program, the Bulgarian authorities believed that they would 'fit in' with the spirit of Soviet Perestroika and give external expression to their slogans of scientific and technical progress and intentions to reform health care.⁹ Last but not least, the Program represented an adequate tool in a period of deteriorating international relations during the Cold War, when the two political blocs competed in developing and supplying each other with increasingly new weapons, in mastering space and the world's oceans, and also in politics, sports, scientific and technical discoveries.

The 'Study of Man and His Brain' Long-term Comprehensive Program: Creation

Occult and political-nationalist approach. The ideologue of the Program was Lyudmila Zhivkova (1942-1981) – daughter of the Bulgarian Communist Party (BCP) leader Todor Zhivkov and until her death the chairperson of the Committee for Culture and the Commission for Science, Culture and Education of the Central Committee of the BCP. As an early 1970s follower of Theosophy and the Agni Yoga teachings in her articles, speeches, and book *'The Intellectual Capacities and Creative Powers of Personality'* (1985)¹⁰ she substantiated the Program through the concept of *'latent reserve capacities/creative endowments of man'*, as it is found in the works of Annie Besant and the family of Nikolai and Elena Roerich. According to Zhivkova, consciousness can expand in all elements of nature and is a factor in the evolution of humanity (the spiral

⁷ COWAN, W.M., D.H. HARTER, E.R. KANDEL. The Emergence of Modern Neuroscience: Some Implications for Neurology and Psychiatry. *Annual Review of Neuroscience*, 2000, vol. 23, pp. 345–346.

⁸ ROCKSTAD-REX, R., P. MAGISTRETTI. An Introduction to the International Brain Research Organization: IBRO's beginnings. *Neurology*, 2012, vol. 79, (14), pp. 1496–1498; MARSHALL, L.H. ET AL. Early History of IBRO: The Birth of Organized Neuroscience. *Neuroscience*, 1996, vol. 72, (1), pp. 283–306; ЖАБЛЕНСКИ, А. Механика на интелекта. *Народна култура*, №8 (1701), 17.02.1989, с. 1, 4.

⁹ ДА – СОФИЯ, ф. 3863, оп. 1, а.е. 16, л. 1-29; а.е. 14, л. 10, 41гр. The start of the Program was accompanied by a Plenum for the Central Committee on the scientific and technical revolution and the developed socialist society (February 12-13, 1985).

¹⁰ ЦДА, ф. 174 Б, оп. 2, а.е. 1433, л. 1а-44.

of ascent). The result must be the harmonious development of man, who will reveal all his abilities and become the master of nature.¹¹

It was with a similar idea that Zhivkova initiated and implemented the Long-Term Comprehensive Program for the Elevation of the Role of Art and Culture for the Harmonious Development of the Personality (1978-1982), for whose patrons she chose so-called ‘*cosmic personalities*’ with universal consciousness and knowledge, i.e. geniuses who changed civilization (V.I. Lenin, Leonardo da Vinci, Nikolai Roerich, and Constantine the Philosopher – St. Cyril).¹² The Program integrated measures in education, culture and the arts and ran in parallel with two other state megaprojects. The first was transnational, also with occult content and directly influenced by Roerich – the ‘*Banner of Peace*’ International Children's Assembly (1979-1984), aimed at talented children from all over the world. The second, ‘*Bulgaria 1300*’, had a nationalist-propaganda orientation and launched the Bulgarian intellectual elites as the natural leaders of the state and society. The ultimate goal of this activity was for Bulgaria to become the center of the sixth race, a higher synthesis of humanity and culture.¹³

A state-managerial and technocratic approach. Along with Zhivkova, Nikola Stefanov (1932-2002) – a philosopher, specialist in social management and cybernetics, high-ranking party official, head of Todor Zhivkov's cabinet, was also considered the creator of the Program. He and his circle of technocrats (engineers, economists, cyberneticists, and biophysicists) developed Zhivkova's ideas in another direction after her death in 1981.¹⁴ They proceeded from modern theories of the nature of the intellect as a unity of brain, psyche, thinking, activity and behavior, but launched the information approach as the leading one. In their view, the reserve capacities of the human personality and brain should be used to harness new technologies, to create robots and artificial

¹¹ Пак там, л. 9.

¹² МИХАЙЛОВА, В. „Големият стартов взрив“. Етапът „Николай Константинович Ръорих“ в контекста на Дългосрочната програма за хармонично развитие на личността. В: Баева, И. (съст.) *Културното отваряне на България към света*. София: УИ, 2013, с. 125–139.

¹³ ЕЛЕНКОВ, ИВ. *Културният фронт. Българската култура през епохата на комунизма – политическо управление, идеологически основания, институционални режими*. София: Сиела, 2008; МИЛЕВ, И. *Животът и смъртта на Людмила Живкова. Биография*. София: Сенс, 2018.

¹⁴ Сф. ЗНЕПОЛСКИ, ИВ. *Българският комунизъм. Социокултурни черти и властова траектория*. София: Сиела, 2008, с. 313-317.

intelligence, to improve control and decision-making systems, and to achieve military objectives.¹⁵ They linked the Program both to new state initiatives, e.g. the reform of psychiatric healthcare and the screening of neurological diseases, and to international factors: cooperation with the West and with the USSR and the socialist bloc.¹⁶

A scientific-medical approach. In 1979-1983, on behalf of the party-state, Zhivkova and Stefanov commissioned a group of Bulgarian medical scientists to develop the Program. Physiologists Ana Varbanova – director of the Brain Research Laboratory at the Bulgarian Academy of Sciences (since 1985 Brain Research Institute – BAS), and Vesselin Petkov – director of the Institute of Physiology at the BAS, as well as scientists from the Medical Academy (MA) – neurologists Dimiter Khadzhiev and Dimiter Chavdarov, and psychiatrists Hristo Hristozov, Asen Jablenski, Toma Tomov, and others, took part in various stages of the process. Their approach to the concept of ‘*hidden human potentials/creative behavior*’ was based on neuroscience, combining its biological and sociocultural interpretation. According to Varbanova, reserves were in fact the adaptive mechanisms for increasing brain tone that can heal and stimulate creativity.¹⁷ According to Jablenski these were the compensatory capacities of the brain under stresses, and according to Petkov – the endorphins that strengthen immune defense.¹⁸ They all spoke of the ‘*mysteries of the brain*’ and of it as an ‘*unexplored universe*’, but from a materialistic and physiological point of view.

A pedagogical-educational approach. As early as the 1960s and later in the early 1980s, Bulgarian pedagogues and educationalists took the initiative to bring back to kindergartens and schools the ideas of new education, strongly advocated in Bulgaria until the middle of the century and stigmatized as ‘*bourgeois*’ and ‘*reactionary*’ by Marxist theorists after 1944. Among them, Prof. Dr. Georgi Lozanov (1926-2012) stood out – a theosophist, head of the Scientific Institute of Suggestology at the Ministry of Education (IS – ME)

¹⁵ ЦДА, ф. 174 Б, оп. 2, а.е. 1433, л. 5-6; СТЕФАНОВ, Н. *Научен подход и социална ситуация*. София: Партиздат, 1983; ЯХИЕЛ, Н. *Социология и социална практика. Социологически анализ на съвременни социални процеси и взаимовръзката им с науката*. София: Наука и изкуство, 1982.

¹⁶ НА – БАН, ф. 74, оп. 6, а.е. 46, л. 20.

¹⁷ КОНДАКОВА, Т. Тайните на мислещата материя. Интервю с А. Върбанова. *Жената днес*, 1985, №4, с. 10-11; НА – БАН, ф. 74, оп. 6, а.е. 46, л. 21.

¹⁸ КАБАКЧИЕВА, Н. Човешката вселена. Разговор с А. Жабленски. *Здраве*, №10, 1986, с. 22-23; ПЕТКОВ, В. Тайните на мозъка. *Здраве*, №3, 1986, с. 16-17.

since 1966. This institution set out to develop the reserve abilities of the human brain through early learning.¹⁹ By 1976, his team organized a number of adult language training courses based on hypnosis and suggestion. In the 1970s, with the strong encouragement of Zhivkova, the methodology was also experimented in secondary schools.²⁰

A second such attempt was made by the Education Task Force, established in 1980 by professors from BAS and Sofia University, educational figures, writers and artists, with the support of the Ministry of Education. The team, headed by mathematics Prof. Blagovest Sendov (1932-2020), set out to achieve all-round personal development through a pilot model of education strongly influenced by the Waldorf anthroposophical schools practised by Rudolf Steiner. It was based on integrative teaching in primary school with an emphasis on children's relationship with nature, arts and new technologies. With state support, the experiment was implemented in a large number of Bulgarian schools and provided by specially designed textbooks and teaching aids and by teacher training.²¹ The institutions of Prof. Lozanov and of Prof. Sendov gave a support to the implementation of the Program.

Structure, management and implementation of the Program. Although defending differing opinions, all described social actors were included in the Program. This reflected on its non-homogeneous content, combining medical, informational and social sciences and humanities; on its unbalanced structure based on 7 problem areas; on the difficult internal interaction between the leading institution – MA, its partner BAS and the co-executors Higher Institute of Physical Education (HIPE) and Sofia University, and ultimately – on the final results achieved. Its administration was even more difficult because, along with scientific units, control was exercised by the Party-state, the military and State Security.

„Hidden Human Potentials/ Creative Endowments’: Utopias

The Program and utopias. The Program proclaimed the desire of its creators for man to become the master of nature and to reach the maximum of his perfection, which was expressed in the eventual realization of a number of uto-

¹⁹ ЦДА, ф. 904, оп. 1, а.е. 3, л. 4; а.е. 31 л. 1; оп. 2, а.е. 41 л. 4-5; а.е. 10, л. 11-12; ВЕЛЕВ, С. Ключ към резервите на мозъка. *Работническо дело*, №277, 04.10.1969, с. 2-3.

²⁰ ЦДА, ф. 904, оп. 2, а.е. 41 л. 5-6, 8-14, 24-29; а.е. 10, л. 5, 7-8.

²¹ Пак там, ф. 1111, оп. 1, а.е. 41, л. 1-6; а.е. 29, л. 1-5, 10-17; а.е. 32, л. 8; а.е. 16, л. 9.

pias: for the prevention and successful treatment of various physical and mental diseases, for increasing life expectancy, activity and the working capacity of the population, to reduce stress, to minimize physical efforts and neutralize bad working conditions, to computerize and robotize the living environment and management, to achieve excellence in learning, art and sports, to develop the creative potential of people. A large part of these social utopias²² were subject to the conjuncture and their achievement was not considered possible even by the initiators of the Program.

(Un)achieved utopias in medicine and healthcare. The Program's 'visible' target groups were children, students, youth, workers and athletes. 'Hidden' actors were the military and intelligence structures.

Given the dominance of medical units in the Program, some real results were achieved in this particular area. Above all, the Program was used to implement methods that have been around since the 1950s-1970s, but were little used in Bulgaria. For example, in the field of neurobiochemistry and molecular biology, methods were tested in cytospectrophotometry and microsurgery, in the preparation of enriched fractions of elements from nervous tissue, for the study of proteins, nucleic acids, lipids and fatty acids in it, enzymatic and radioimmunomethods were applied.²³

Scientists from the Central Brain Research Laboratory – BAS, MA and the District Psychodispensary in Vratsa conducted tests for neurological diseases according to the English pattern, studied children's intellectual and speech pathologies, visual disorders and language development in the Northern Bulgaria and specifically in institutions in the Pleven district (1987)²⁴. They were supported by the Laboratory of Education at Sofia University. Teams from Brain Research Institute – BAS (BRI) and MA in collaboration with the WHO and the Institute of Psychiatry in London screened 6,000 pupils in grades 1-2 for psychosocial development and specifically for the presence of Cyrillic dyslexia

²² The Bulgarian communist regime is no exception in its claims that it will create an ideal 'new world' with 'new people' modeled by the state according to its visions. Cf. БРУНБАУЕР, У. За отношенията между държава и общество в комунистическа България. В: Знеполски, Ив., (Съст.) Тоталитаризмите на XX в. в сравнителна перспектива. София: Сиела, 2010, с. 185-186.

²³ ВЕНКОВ, Л. Методики в областта на биохимията и молекулярната биология и тяхното внедряване за нуждите на Програмата. *Програма за комплексно изучаване на човека и неговия мозък*, св. 1, 1986, с. 22-32.

²⁴ НА – БАН, ф. 74, оп. 6, а.е. 52а, л. 13-14.

and fine motor skills (1986-1988). As a result, a school compensation and remedial program was developed and a dyslexia treatment office opened.²⁵ Scientists from BAS and MA conducted a representative epidemiological study of the mental health of children aged 8.5-9.5 years and developed a methodology for controlling ‘*problem pupils*’ with hyperactivity and unsustainable attention (1988-1990).²⁶ In some auxiliary schools (for children with disabilities), teams of psychiatrists and psychologists from the IS – ME (included in the Program from the beginning, then removed from it and transformed as a Laboratory at Sofia University) examined for oligophrenia, infantilism and speech disorders.²⁷

In 1986, at the Scientific Institute of Neurology, Psychiatry and Neurosurgery at MA (SINPN – MA), the first steps were taken in reflexology for multiple sclerosis, in the biochemical diagnosis of mental deficiency, depressions and in art therapy.²⁸ In 1988, a methodology was developed for the early detection (screening) of preclinical manifestations of atherosclerosis, which was introduced as a pilot in two Sofia polyclinics.²⁹

The SINPN – MA started targeted training of young psychiatrists, psychologists and neurologists in family psychotherapy, psychodrama, medical psychology, non-alcoholic addictions and pedagogical rehabilitation.³⁰ These methods alongside with cultural therapy, physical therapy, physiotherapy, acupuncture, work with alcohol addicts were introduced in 1986-1988 in the psychiatric dispensaries of Sofia and of Sofia district.³¹ A Cabinet for neuroses, logoneuroses and psychoses was also opened there, and follow-ups of children with chronic alcoholic parents who suffered from inflammatory diseases of the central nervous system were carried out.³²

At BAS, MA and HIPE, quite a few stimulants or sedatives were developed and tested, intended for competitors in weightlifting, wrestling, swim-

²⁵ ДА – СОФИЯ, ф. 3863, оп. 1, а.е. 87, л. 1-14; а.е. 16, л. 3-4.

²⁶ Пак там, а.е. 15, л. 6-7; а.е. 17, л. 91-93; НА – БАН, ф. 74, оп. 6, а.е. 67, л. 32; РАЙНОВ, В. „Живи са още онези, които са ги видели“. София: Мултипринт, 2021, с. 29-31.

²⁷ ЦДА, ф. 904, оп. 2, а.е. 41, л. 32.

²⁸ Пак там, ф. 517, оп. 8, а.е. 9, л. 31-34.

²⁹ ДА – СОФИЯ, ф. 3863, оп. 1, а.е. 87, л. 1-14.

³⁰ Пак там, ф. 1742, оп. 2, а.е. 26, л. 42; а.е. 27, л. 25-27, 53; ф. 1712, оп. 3, а.е. 13 л. 5-6, 8, 23; оп. 3, а.е. 12, л. 12, 19, 58-59, 85-86.

³¹ Пак там, а.е. 12, л. 69, 12, 58-59.

³² Пак там, а.е. 13, л. 5; ф. 1742, оп. 2, а.е. 26, л. 9-11; а.е. 27, л. 46.

ming, athletics, etc.³³ They were the necessary doping for Bulgarian sport to be at the forefront. Scientists from BRI – BAS studied the experience of Czechoslovakia and Georgia in the meditation of yogis with a view to the recovery or concentration of athletes (1984-1987).³⁴

In fact, the greatest achievements of the Program were in space and underwater (marine) medicine, where a group of institutes from the BAS studied human capabilities under overload from high pressures, weightlessness, irradiation, radiation, building, lack of sleep, etc.³⁵ They were used to develop new weapons and for intelligence purposes.

In the field of medical neuroscience, not all intentions had been fulfilled. The most significant obstacle was the unpreparedness of the majority of scientists to work with new theoretical and methodological tools that have widely entered into practice in the US, France, England, Japan, etc. The reasons for this were the state policy of scientific isolationism, fundamentally limiting the access of Bulgarian scientists to scholarships (of the Humboldt or Fulbright Foundations, of the UNESCO, the WHO, the IAEA, the IBRO, the European Science Foundation, etc.), giving priority to the USSR and the Eastern Bloc countries in long-term specializations, providing relatively little access to up-to-date scientific information, and banning collective membership in leading scientific organizations. A serious obstacle was also the lack or delayed purchase of consumables (materials, chemicals, isotopes and serums) and equipment (ultracentrifuges, spectrophotometers, gamma counters, refrigerators, computers, etc.).³⁶

(Un)achieved utopias in education and science. The Institute of Cybernetics and Robotics – BAS studied the implementation of ICT among children. A Center for Giftedness and Creativity was established at the Scientific Institute of Education, which conducted trainings with teachers, and scientists from the BAS studied the effect of music therapy and integral training for developing intellectual potential in children and school age, for memorizing, listening, read-

³³ НА – БАН, ф. 74, оп. 6, а.е. 37, л. 3; ЦДА, ф. 1Б, оп. 71, а.е. 3857, л. 300; БОГДАНОВА, Н. *Достоен за рекордите на Гинес*. София: Типтоп прес, 2002, с. 131.

³⁴ НА – БАН, ф. 74, оп. 6, а.е. 40, л. 1; а.е. 53, л. 36-41.

³⁵ ЦДА, ф. 517, оп. 8, а.е. 9, л. 31-34; оп. 5с, а.е. 7, л. 3гр., 16, 20; НА – БАН, ф. 74, оп. 6, а.е. 37, л. 15-22.

³⁶ ВЕНКОВ, Л. Цит.съч., с. 33-35; Нова съвременна апаратура. *Здравен фронт*, №20, 16.05.1987; ЗДРАВЕН ФРОНТ, №24, 13.06.1987.

ing and creating of habits.³⁷ The National Educational Complex for Culture at Gorna Banya district became a base for experimental research.

The Central Laboratory of Psychology – BAS also worked for the benefit of developing children's talents. It adapted Paul Torrance's Creative Thinking Tests, M. Apter's Questionnaires for Stable Motivational Characteristics, D. Jenkins' Behavioral Assessment Questionnaire, and the Adolescent Self-Imagination Survey (QSIQ). R. Mailey's test for assessing the intelligence of young children was also tested.³⁸

A support for the Program was provided by the existing Task Force for Education led by Prof. Sendov, which, in cooperation with the Laboratory of Education at Sofia University, implemented its model of integrative education in 28 schools, covering 5,266 students and 1,154 teachers, introduced new curricula and textbooks emphasizing advanced study in the arts, sports, information technology, and foreign languages.³⁹

The Program provided participating institutions with a huge financial resource, incomparable to previous budgets, which made it possible to send scientists to international conferences, for their regular specializations abroad, to create networking with world organizations, to purchase modern equipment, software and reagents and for the supply of current scientific literature. Thanks to her, the country's regular membership in IBRO, International Society for the Study of Behavioral Development (ISSOD) and the European Coordinating Committee on Artificial Intelligence was formed as first steps towards real internationalization and global integration in world science.⁴⁰ The Program stimulated integration processes internally as well: the Bulgarian Neuroscience Society (1987-1988) with 186 members and the Bulgarian Psychiatric Association (1991) were successively established.⁴¹

Two dozens of doctoral students were trained under the Program, who in the following decades made an upward career in the country and in international institutions. To this day, they talk very positively about their *‘flying’*

³⁷ Час по мислене. Интелектът и „методът на очилата“. *Народна култура*, №31, 02.08.1985.

³⁸ БЪЛГАРСКО СПИСАНИЕ ПО ПСИХОЛОГИЯ, 2014, №4, с. 14, 91.

³⁹ ЦДА, ф. 1111, оп. 1, а.е. 32, л. 8; а.е. 16, л. 9.

⁴⁰ НА – БАН, ф. 74, оп. 6, а.е. 61, л. 54-56; а.е. 53, л. 12-32; ЦДА, ф. 1Б, оп. 71, а.е. 1494, л. 1; ДА – СОФИЯ, ф. 3863, оп. 1, а.е. 16, л. 9.

⁴¹ ЗДРАВЕН ФРОНТ, №29, 18.07.1987; ХРИСТОЗОВ, ХР. Цит.съч., с. 256; ЦДА, ф. 1565, оп.1, а.е. 11, л. 1-3.

start in science and about the benefits they had from the Program: the acquisition of confidence and new knowledge, the ‘*expanded horizons*‘ through the innovative topics and trainings from leading foreign specialists, the contacts with Bulgarian colleagues and foreign scientists at seminars, trainings, training courses; the visited scientific forums and specializations in universities of Central and Western Europe.⁴²

In 1985-1990, through the Program, the project style of scientific work and funding was tested for the first time in Bulgaria, which was supposed to create an alternative to the existing hierarchy in ‘socialist‘ science, where the topics were determined from above (the Party, state, institution, and principal), their performance was strictly monitored, but was tied only to the salary, and the results were subject to evaluation only within the institutes. The introduction of a competitive approach, the formation of temporary teams of members from various institutions, not subject to the control of formal superiors, the link between results and salary, the inclusion of external reviewers – these were small ‘*revolutions*‘ in the conservative structure of science and in the thinking of certain individuals.⁴³

At the same time, the work of the Program teams encountered a number of difficulties: stumbling blocks and attempts at direct control by directors; unification of scientists from different units whose manner of work and methodology were incompatible; favoring certain scientists with party and administrative positions at the expense of non-party ones.⁴⁴ The impossibility of breaking with the current mechanism of science management was visible mostly in the financial issues: the envisaged budgets were not compatible with the current legislation and based on disproportions between the share of expenses for team’s payments (on average 85%) and those intended for administration; all costs for working equipment and consumables were managed by the MA.⁴⁵ Some of

⁴² Standardized interviews with: K.A., male, 1960, then doctoral student, now Professor; K.T., female, 1957, then young scholar, now Professor; I.Y., female, 1959, then doctoral student, now Professor; T.C., male, 1953, then doctoral student, now Professor; M.V., female, 1957, then young scholar, now Professor; R.V., male, 1942, then research fellow, now Professor; K.V., then research fellow, now Professor. In: Personal archive of the author, 2023-2024; Semi-standardized interviews with: J.V., male, 1961, then doctoral student, now Professor; T.V., male, 1958, Associate Professor. In: Personal archive of the author, 2022-2023.

⁴³ ДА – СОФИЯ, ф. 3863, оп. 1, а.е. 16, л. 9-10.

⁴⁴ Пак там, л. 21-23; а.е. 87, л. 1-14.

⁴⁵ ХРИСТОЗОВ, ХР. Цит. съч., с. 247; ТОДОРОВ, Н. *Дневник, 1966-1998*. Т. 2. София: Изток-Запад, 2007, с. 1555; НА – БАН, ф. 74, оп. 6, а.е. 46, л. 23; а.е. 42, л. 21; а.е. 49, л. 22-24, 33-34.

the participants felt that their work remained ‘invisible’ because the results of the research remained unpublished - the short project deadlines could not be reconciled with the slow editing process practiced by the then state publishing houses and especially in scientific periodicals.⁴⁶

(Un)achieved utopias in the economy and labor. Although two of the problem areas of the Program were directly aimed at the organization and working conditions, the results of military experiments and especially of the hyperbaric and space projects of the ‘*Intermozak*’ (‘*Inter Brain*’) and ‘*Interkosmos*’ (‘*Inter Cosmos*’) International Programs developed under the auspices of the USSR were mainly implemented with the participation of the Eastern Bloc countries. They treated the effects of immobilization, exposure to adverse factors (high pressure), vestibular instability, etc.

‘*Visible*’ results were significantly fewer and rarely implemented. The medical units of the BAS studied the relationship between brain hyperactivity, stress and memory and developed a methodology for diagnosing stress and stress genic functional disorders in a work environment (1990).⁴⁷ A project was devoted to the optimization of the working environment for working with computers.⁴⁸ The team of the Laboratory of Psychology – BAS and of the Sofia University adapted the questionnaire STAI (State – Trait Anxiety Inventory) of Ch. Spielberger, measuring anxiety (1989).⁴⁹ In the Department of Physiotherapy of the MA, the rehabilitation of workers affected by work accidents and paresis began.

(Un)achieved utopias in cybernetics and social governance. The Program was conceived as strategic with a view to social governance, but that is where it failed to achieve its goals. This was due both to the weak integration of social and information sciences and the practical ‘*encapsulation*’ of teams, as well as to the significant ideological limitations placed on sociology, psychology and philosophy.

Therefore, the BAS institutes of cybernetics and robotics focused mainly on military or applied developments: algorithms for machine modeling of mem-

⁴⁶ The Program published volumes of its eponymous science and information review (1986-1990).

⁴⁷ ЦДА, ф. 517, оп. 8, а.е. 9, л. 31-34; ДА – СОФИЯ, ф. 3863, оп. 1, а.е. 87, л. 1-14.

⁴⁸ Пак там, а.е. 15, л. 6-7.

⁴⁹ ЩЕТИНСКИ, Д. ЗА приятеля Иван Паспаланов и съвместната ни работа. *Българско списание по психология*, 2014, №4, с. 14.

ory processes (1987) and expert systems in biotechnology based on the principle of artificial intelligence; a new programming language for data analysis in neurophysiology.⁵⁰ For their part, the institutes of Sociology and of Philosophy started but did not complete or implement their projects, e.g. for learning the values of a socialist way of life (1986), for adapting Alex Inkeles's Personal Modernization Questionnaire based on a nationally representative empirical sociological survey, and for adding the American sociologist Dwayne Alvin's methodology for notions of justice⁵¹. Probably because of the low efficiency, the idea of optimizing management by creating single complexes of culture, science and education, which would be directly subordinated to the Political Bureau of the BCP, was rejected.

Conclusion

Unlike the Program for the Development of Hidden Superpowers and Human Abilities, curated by the Ministry of Defense of the USSR in the 1980s, the Bulgarian Program was public and did not serve only military purposes. However, it, like the Soviet one, was inspired by occult circles and, in addition to its *'visible'* goals, contained *'hidden'* ones. The main emphasis of the Program was placed on man's *'hidden human potentials/ creative endowments'*, which the leaders and ideologues of the Program understood as a basic occult theosophical concept, but presented it in the scientific terms of behaviorism, cognitive science, cybernetics, and cultural anthropology. Although the goals of the Program were formulated as promoting personal self-improvement, increasing human abilities to read, write, learn and think, develop interests and creative behavior and ultimately create a *'harmoniously developed personality'*, it had parallels more in the Western world: in the international programs of the WHO 'Health for All' and the prevention of socially significant diseases, in the European Science Foundation's Brain Program (1988-1990) and in the Decade of the Brain in the USA (1990-1999).⁵²

The Program represented both an attempt to reform Bulgarian science, health care and secondary education based on the transfer of knowledge, technique and technology from the Western Europe and the US, and to realize

⁵⁰ ДА – СОФИЯ, ф. 3863, оп. 1, а.е. 87, л. 1-14; ПРОГРАМА за комплексно изучаване на човека и неговия мозък. *Обзори*, св. 2, 1987, с. 65-67.

⁵¹ НА - БАН, ф. 154К, оп. 1, а.е. 457; Standardized interview with K.T., female, 1957, then young scientist, now Professor. In: Personal archive of the author.

⁵² ДА – СОФИЯ, ф. 3863, оп. 1, а.е. 15, л. 35-37.

significant social utopias. For a number of reasons, it was mainly oriented towards the small (educational and professional) social groups and had minimal impact on the large (age) groups (children and the elderly). The partial results achieved, due to the beginning of the political and economic transition and ineffective organization, were important from the perspective of social reformation, but not from the point of view of reaching the targeted utopias.

The significant impact of the Program can be found mainly in the field of science, because it represented an attempt to institutionally consolidate (from above) neuroscience and to quickly position it in an interdisciplinary environment. Through the transfer of knowledge, it initiated or dynamized a number of existing modern medical methodologies, practices and scientific research. However, the Program did not create the desired interdisciplinarity in Bulgarian science.

The hypothesis of some researchers about the use of the Program for the purposes of social engineering⁵³, i.e. the possibility of creating new social elites⁵⁴ through it, who would reform communist society ‘*from within*’ through their new mentality, based on the ‘*reserve potentials*’ of the personality, are not confirmed. If such visions were nevertheless laid down in its occult basis in the early 1980s, they were pushed to the background in the process of constructing the Program and completely eliminated in the course of its implementation, especially in the 1990s. The dominant majority of the young and habilitated scientists/scholars covered by the Program had a materialistic worldview and communist views, and were not at all interested in occult ideas. Their leading motivation was pragmatic – for personal and career development, and in the following decades they remained in science, and did not become ruling political elites.

⁵³ МЕТОДИЕВА, Ю. Социалното инженерство на българския тоталитаризъм е родило шедеври. Интервю с Румен Петров. *Маргиналия*, 17.01.2020. Достъпна на: <https://www.marginalia.bg/aktsent/shedovar-na-totalitarniya-rezhim/>, 11.05.2025; ИВАНОВА, Д. 1984 и Програмата за мозъка: 40 години по-късно. *Свободна Европа*, 01.04.2023. Достъпна на: <https://www.svobodnaevropa.bg/a/32343410.html>, 11.05.2025. For the implementation of true social engineering through higher education, see БОЯДЖИЕВА, П. *Социалното инженерство: политики за прием във висшите училища през комунистическия режим в България*. София: Сиела, 2010.

⁵⁴ For the social structure of Bulgaria in this period, see КАБАКЧИЕВА, П. *Комунистическа идеология, социална структура и социални неравенства в България*. В: ЗНЕПОЛСКИ, ИВ. (СЪСТ.) *История на Народна република България. Режимът и обществото*. София: Сиела, 2009, с. 438-480.

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Prof. Georgeta Nazarska, Ph.D.
University of Library Studies and IT, Sofia
119, Tsarigradsko shosse Blvd., 1784, Sofia
e-mail georgeta.nazarska@gmail.com
ORCID ID 0000-0002-6448-3692
Researcher ID 24344794500